

Target directed enediyne : Chemical and biological significance[†]

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Abstract : The novel chemical framework and potent antitumor activity of the enediyne natural products such as calicheamicin, dynemicin, esperamicin, and neocarzinostatin has fostered interest in the development of simple enediynes with low thermal cyclization temperature. It is well established that thermally labial enediynes exhibit anticancer activity, while there are few scattered examples in the literature about the biological importance of thermally stable enediynes. The present article deals with the synthesis, thermal reactivity of metalloenediynes, and antibacterial activity of thermally stable cyclic enediynes.

Keywords : Endowment lecture, enediynes, thermal reactivity, cyclization, antibacterial activity, copper complexes.

Introduction

First discovered in 1972, Bergman cyclization is a thermally allowed electronic rearrangement of Z-3-ene-1,5-diyne to a 1,4-didehydrobenzene diradical which after quenching by hydrogen source affords a new benzene ring (Scheme 1)^{1,2}.

Scheme 1

Prior to Bergman's studies Masamune *et al.*³ described the conversion of the cyclic enediyne to benzenoid systems, without mentioning the involvement of the diradical intermediate. Later, Wong and Sondheimer⁴ had also observed the cycloaromatization of the strained cyclic enediynes and postulated benzenoid-1,4-diradical as an intermediate. However, this novel reaction received little attention until the early 1980's and underwent renaissance after the structural elucidation of natural product antibiotics such as calicheamicin⁵, esperamicins⁶, and dynemicin⁷. All these compounds contain an enediyne moiety, and exerts their biological action due to their ability to form diradical^{1,2}, which abstract hydrogen atom from the DNA back bone and causes cell death⁸⁻¹⁹. This

class of compounds got immediate attention of the biologist, due to their fascinating mode of action and that of chemist, due to their novel molecular framework. Number of approaches such as synthetic^{20,21}, photochemical²²⁻²⁶ and electrochemical²³ have been explored in order to initiate the Bergman cyclization reactions in a controlled manner.

Nicolaou *et al.*^{27,28} postulated that the ease of the cycloaromatization of the enediynes can be estimated from the distance between alkyne carbon termini (1-3).

But, Snyder²⁹ had pointed out that the reactivity of the strained enediyne is largely determined by the difference of the strain energy between transition and ground state. Accordingly, strained enediynes with a rather short alkyne carbon termini distance might still be stable if the transition state suffers from even higher strain. It is also reported that electronic factor also influence the rate of Bergman cyclizations³⁰⁻³³. Russell *et al.*³⁴ observed that

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the electron deficient heteroarenediynes (**4-6**) have lower activation energy compared to substituted 1,2-diethynylbenzenes^{35,36}.

$t_{1/2}$ = 148 min, 152 °C $t_{1/2}$ = 13 min, 155 °C $t_{1/2}$ = 7 min, 154 °C

In the quinone/hydroquinone systems, it was observed that quinone system (**7-9**) containing enediynes undergo Bergman cyclization much faster than their hydroquinone counterpart (**10,11**)³⁷⁻⁴⁰. Electron withdrawing groups attached to the alkyne carbon termini lowers the activation energy of the cycloaromatizations, while electron donating substituent inhibit the cyclization of the enediynes³³. It has also been proposed that the amount of the double bond character in the double bond along with the distance between the diyne termini determines the activation energy required for cyclization³⁷. This was based on the fact that arenediynes generally have lower thermal reactivity than their nonaromatic counterparts³⁸. Maier *et al.*²¹, reported that electron donating arene attached to the double bond inhibited the cyclization of the resulting enediynes.

$t_{1/2}$ = 32 min, 55 °C $t_{1/2}$ = 2.6 h, 55 °C $t_{1/2}$ = 88 h, 40 °C

$t_{1/2}$ = >7 d, 120 °C $t_{1/2}$ = >1 d, 120 °C

Recently, Jones *et al.*⁴¹ measured the $t_{1/2}$ for nine membered chloro substituted enediyne (**12**) while parent nine membered enediyne is not known, same author also showed that substitution of olefin proton with chlorine inhibit the cyclization temperature of the resulting enediynes (**13**). In general the evidence supporting the double bond character not very clear.

X = H, Unknown compound
X = Cl, $t_{1/2}$ = 8 h, 0 °C

X = Cl, Y = H, $t_{1/2}$ = 5 h, 60 °C
X = Cl, Y = Cl, $t_{1/2}$ = 24 h, 170 °C

More recently, another approach that involved the metal ions has been used for the activations of the enediyne (Fig. 1)⁴²⁻⁴⁸. König reported that crown ether containing enediyne undergoes cyclization at higher temperature after complexation with sodium or potassium (**14**)⁴⁹. Later in 1995 Buchwald⁴² and König⁴³ reported that the enediyne cyclization temperature could be dropped significantly by metal ion coordination. Buchwald showed that dppeb ligand after complexation with the Pd or Pt undergoes Bergman cyclization at much lower temperature than the uncomplexed ligand (**15**)⁴². Likewise König reported that bipyridyl enediyne after complexation with Hg cyclizes at 142 °C while uncomplexed ligand cyclizes at 243 °C (**16**)⁴³. Salen based enediyne ligand synthesized by Basak *et al.*⁴⁸ undergoes cyclization at higher temperature on complexation with metal (**17**). The present account deals the work done by the author in this area in last 6-7 years.

Cyclization Temperature enediyne: 142 °C
Cyclization Temperature metal complex: 160 °C

Cyclization Temperature enediyne: 243 °C
Cyclization Temperature metal complex: 61 °C

Cyclization Temperature enediyne: 240 °C
Cyclization Temperature metal complex: 141 °C

Cyclization Temperature enediyne: 156 °C
Cyclization Temperature metal complex: 234 °C

Fig. 1. Metalloenediynes.

Bidentate enediyne ligands and their copper complexes

Flexible enediyne system

Flexible enediyne ligand 1,8-bis(pyridin-3-oxy)oct-4-ene-2,6-diyne (bpod, **18**)⁵⁰ was prepared by the fast addition of 1,8-dibromooct-4-ene-2,6-diyne⁵¹ to a stirred solution of 3-hydroxypyridine and KOH in DMF (Scheme 2). The reaction mixture was washed with water and the product was extracted with dichloromethane. Compound **18** was then purified by flash chromatography and characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data. Due to the instability of 1,8-dibromooct-4-ene-2,6-diyne⁵¹ in the reaction conditions, yield of the product decreased if 1,8-dibromooct-4-ene-2,6-diyne was added slowly. An alternative two step method⁵² for the synthesis of this novel compound has also been developed, which involves the preparation of 3-prop-2-ynoxy-pyridine⁵³ followed by coupling with *cis*-1,2-dichloroethylene in presence of Pd⁰, Cu^I and *n*-BuNH₂ in benzene (Scheme 2). Usual work up and purification by column chromatography gave analytically pure compound (**18**). This method did not require bromoenediyne which requires bromine as key reagent to make and is lachrymatory.

The Cu^I complex (**19**) was prepared by reacting **18**

Scheme 2

with [Cu(CH₃CN)₄PF₆] in 2 : 1 molar ratio in degassed acetonitrile under nitrogen atmosphere (Scheme 3)⁵⁰. The compound was obtained as a yellow solid after adding ether in the reaction mixture. The Cu^{II} complex (**21**) was prepared by reacting 1 equiv of Cu(NO₃)₂ and 2 equiv of the enediyne ligand (**18**) as a green powder. The neutral compound Cu(bpod)Cl₂ (**20**) was obtained by reacting CuCl₂ with bpod in a 1 : 1 molar ratio in MeOH followed by repeated washings by ether (Scheme 3). These compounds were characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR, elemen-

Scheme 3

tal analyses and mass spectrometry.

Thermal reactivity

The thermal reactivity of the enediyne (**18**) and copper metalloenediynes (**19-21**) were determined in solution and in solid state⁵⁰. On heating compound **18** at 90 °C in DMSO-*d*₆ in the presence of 1,4-cyclohexadiene, no reaction was observed after 7 h, but on increasing temperature to 120 °C decomposition of **18** was observed in 8 h. The Cu^I complex (**19**) undergoes Bergman cyclization at 90 °C after heating for 8 h (*t*_{1/2} = 5.3 h, Scheme 3). Formation of the Bergman cyclized product was confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C NMR, which showed the disappearance of the olefinic proton at 5.90 ppm and OCH₂ proton at 4.89 ppm and appearance of the new singlet at 5.40 ppm for the methylene group attached with oxygen and benzene ring. Furthermore in ¹³C NMR spectrum resonance for the alkyne carbon at 84.67, 90.0 ppm and olefin carbon at 119.80 ppm were disappeared and new resonances were observed at 68.9 (OCH₂Ph), and 129.9, 130.3 and 136.4 ppm for the di-substituted benzene. The cyclized product (**22**) formation was further confirmed by mass spectrometry which showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* = 647.2. Similarly, cyclization of Cu^{II} complex (**21**) in solution was also confirmed by heating at 60 °C for 12 h. The formation of Bergman cyclized product was confirmed after extraction of the metal with EDTA due to diamagnetic nature of Cu^{II} center and subsequent characterization of the organic compound **23**. The structure of the organic compound was determined with the help of ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and mass spectral data.

Thermal reactivity of these compounds was also studied in solid state by differential scanning calorimetry. The free ligand undergoes for Bergman cyclization at 136 °C as a neat oil, while Cu^I shows an exothermic peak at 203 °C and Cu^{II} at 121 °C, but CuCl₂ compound showed reactivity at 153 °C. The variation of the thermal reactivity of these copper complexes have been ascribed to geometric structural differences between N₄ and N₂Cl₂ inner sphere coordination to copper.

Rigid enediyne system

Thermal reactivity comparison between the acyclic enediynes showed that more conformationally flexible the ligand, as defined by the greater number of sp³ carbon atoms in between metal binding functionality and alkyne termini, lower the cyclization temperature. But the greater response due to metal coordination was observed for the rigid enediyne systems, as for example *dppd* (which is

the only known organic enediyne in which metal binding functionality is directly attached with the alkyne carbon) undergo for Bergman cyclization at 243 °C but upon complexation with Pd or Pt resulting metal complex cyclizes at 61 °C and 82 °C respectively⁴². In order to study the affect of rigidity on Bergman cyclization temperatures using single metal in different oxidation states in a specific ligand, we designed new set of the rigid enediyne ligands based on 3-ethynylpyridine⁵⁴. The starting materials 3-ethynylpyridine was prepared by the modified literature method⁵⁵.

The enediyne ligand 1,6-bis(pyridin-3)-hex-ene-1,5-diyne⁵⁵ (**25**) was prepared by the addition of 2.2 equiv of 3-ethynylpyridine (**24**) to *cis*-1,2-dichloroethylene over Pd⁰ catalyst, in the presence of the CuI and *n*-BuNH₂ in benzene at 40–45 °C (Scheme 4). It was observed that at room temperature this reaction was very slow and yield of the product was poor, but at 40–45 °C reaction proceeds very fast and completed within 1 h. Furthermore, slow addition of the alkyne was necessary, otherwise yield of the product was poor, due to the decomposition of the alkyne in the reaction conditions. Crude product was purified by flash chromatography.

The Cu^{II} complex **26** of the enediyne ligand **25** was prepared by reacting a 2:1 molar ratio of the enediyne ligand with Cu(NO₃)₂ in MeOH at ambient temperature. The analogous CuN₂Cl₂ compound **28** was prepared by reacting enediyne ligand (**25**) with Cu₂Cl₂.2H₂O in a 1:1 molar ratio. The corresponding Cu^I complex (**27**) was prepared by the reaction of **25** with [Cu(CH₃CN)₄]PF₆ in a 2 : 1 molar ratio in degassed MeOH under a nitrogen atmosphere (Scheme 4). The structure of these compounds were confirmed by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, elemental analyses and mass spectrometry⁵⁵.

Thermal reactivity

The solid-state thermal reactivity of the enediynes (**25**) and their copper complexes (**26-28**) were measured by DSC. The enediyne (**25**) undergoes for Bergman cyclization at 194 °C and its copper complexes cyclizes at varied temperature. For example the DSC profile of (PyED)₂Cu^{II} (**26**), CuCl₂(PyED) (**28**), and (PrED)₂Cu^I (**27**) showed the exothermic peak at 156 °C, 256 °C and 326 °C respectively, indicating stabilization of the enediyne unit proceeding from [Cu(enediyne)₂]²⁺ to Cu(enediyne)Cl₂ and [Cu(enediyne)₂]⁺. Structure of these complexes were determined by solid state UV-Vis spectroscopy. The UV-Vis spectrum of (PyED)₂Cu^{II} (**26**) ex-

Scheme 4

hibits a maximum at 16284 cm^{-1} which can be deconvoluted using three Gaussian band shapes centered at 17626 , 16009 and 14351 cm^{-1} . The overall energy profile for a system with N_4 legation indicate that the structure is 6-coordinate with little distortion from an octahedral ligand field. Indeed, the structural assignment is corroborated by mass spectrometry and elemental analysis, which show that the compound is prepared as a 6-coordinate with two coordinated nitrate counter ions. In contrast, the d-d transitions (16943 ; 14706 ; 12501 cm^{-1}) that comprises the absorption profile ($E_{\text{max}} = 14519\text{ cm}^{-1}$) for the dichloride analogue $(\text{PyED})\text{CuCl}_2$ (**28**) are red shifted relative to **26** by $1300\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This can be accounted by two distinct structural differences between the divalent dichloride and their bis(enediyne) counterparts. First, mass spectrometry and elemental analysis indicate that (**28**) is a neutral 4-coordinate compound in the solid state. Reduction in coordination number from 6 to 4 in a tetragonal Cu^{II} system generally increases the ligand field splitting of the d-manifold and consequently the energy of the ligand field transitions. Second, the limited steric bulk of the chlorides, coupled with the charge donation to the Cu^{II} center, results in *cis*- CuN_2Cl_2 complex that typically exhibit considerable dihedral angle distortion. Typically 4-coordinate *cis*- CuN_2Cl_2 structures with pseudo tetrahedral geometries exhibit absorption

maximum between $11000\text{--}14000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the structure for $(\text{PyED})\text{CuCl}_2$ (**28**) is best described as 4-coordinate tetrahedron where the dihedral angle lies between planar and tetrahedral geometries. The solid state structure proposed for (**28**) from the spectroscopic data is sensible since $>75\%$ of the *cis*- CuN_2Cl_2 structure in the Cambridge Database exhibit degrees of distortion in this range. The intermediate degree of distortion is also consistent with the solid state Bergman cyclization temperature for $(\text{PyED})\text{CuCl}_2$ (**28**) which is in between those of tetrahedral Cu^{I} and tetragonal Cu^{II} geometries.

Molecular mechanics/dynamics calculations

In an effort to determine the role of the copper center geometry on modulation of the alkyne termini separation, structures of these complexes (**19,21**) were calculated using direct energy minimization. Several of the lowest energy structures were then used as initial structures for molecular dynamics simulations to estimate the ground state structures under ambient conditions. In the dynamics simulations, the protocol allows the starting structures to access the thermal bath modes at 800 K prior to cooling to a final sample temperature of 300 K . For the Cu^{I} complex, as predicted by ligand field theory, tetrahedral geometry of the CuN_4 core is the dominant lowest energy structure and constantly reproduced from

all initial geometric starting points. The average alkyne termini distance $\langle a \rangle$ was then calculated from an ensemble of the five tetrahedral structures lowest in energy. The relative energies of these structures span 8 kcal/mol, with a modest standard deviation in the mean energy of 2.9%. From this structural subset, $\langle a \rangle$ was determined to be 4.0 Å for Cu^I (**19**). The same dynamics approach was used for the Cu^{II} complex (**21**). The alkyne termini distance was determined $\langle a \rangle$ 3.6 Å. The thermal reactivity difference between (**19**) and (**21**) shows that the tetrahedral geometry of (**19**) causes significant distortion of the enediyne unit and force the alkyne termini to a greater separation distance (0.4 Å), than the less strained tetragonal structure of (**21**). Thus, the distance between alkyne carbon termini can be intimately mediated by the geometric requirements of the metal center, resulting in profound effects upon the thermal reactivity of the metalloenediyne complex.

The variation of oxidation state of the metal center in flexible enediyne cause the 73 °C difference in the cyclization temperature between (bpod)₂Cu^I (**19**) and (bpod)₂Cu^{II} (**21**), but in the rigid metalloenediyne system (**26,27**) this difference was too high (170 °C). So in order to determine if structural consequences can account for the dramatic 170 °C in the rigid enediyne systems, structures of the rigid and their metal complexes were also determined by same approach. The average separation of alkyne termini for (PyED)₂Cu^I (**27**) was calculated from

the four tetrahedral structures lowest in energy. The relative energies of these structures range 5.6 kcal/mol with a modest standard deviation in the mean energy of 2.5%. From this structural subset $\langle a \rangle$ was determined to be 4.20 Å for **27** which correlates well with the high thermal requirement for Bergman cyclization of this complex and the coarse relationship between distance and cyclization temperature for synthetic enediynes. By the same approach the distance in (PyED)₂Cu^{II} (**26**) was calculated to be 3.85 Å and for the neutral compound PyEDCuCl₂ (**28**) 4.07 Å. Interestingly, within the 0.35 Å range in $\langle a \rangle$ between Cu^{II} and Cu^I, the $\langle a \rangle$ value for CuCl₂ falls 37% from that of Cu^I. A nearly identical deviation (36%) is observed in the Bergman cyclization temperature of CuCl₂ relative to Cu^I, indicating that the variation of distance with structure is at least partially responsible for the observed thermal reactivity's of these copper metalloenediynes.

Steric effects on Bergman cyclization

From the original synthetic work it has been proposed that the main factor which affects the Bergman cyclization reactions were distance between alkyne carbon termini^{27,28}, electronic effects³⁰⁻³³ and size of the ring⁴¹. But little was known if steric bulk at the metal binding functionality can affect the cyclization temperature in the enediyne. So we have designed ligands having same molecular framework but change the steric bulk at the metal

Scheme 5

binding functionality and study if steric effect can change the thermal reactivity of the resulting enediyne ligands. Four enediynes having different steric bulk at alkyne carbon termini such as 1,8-bis(dimethylamino)oct-4-ene-2,6-diyne (**33**)^{57,58} two asymmetric enediyne (**35,36**)⁵⁸ and 1,8-diaminooct-4-ene-2,6-diyne (**40**) were synthesized (Scheme 5)⁵⁸.

In general Pd⁰ catalyzed coupling of the alkyne (**29,30**) with *cis*-dichloroethylene in 2:1 molar ratio gave bis(dimethylamino)enediyne (**33**) and reaction in 1:1 ratio of alkyne with *cis*-dichloroethylene led the formation of chloro-ene-yne compounds (**31,32**) (Scheme 5). Further coupling of the chloro-ene-yne compound with appropriate alkyne gave the asymmetric enediynes (**35,36**).

Scheme 6

Our efforts to make diamino enediyne (**40**) without protecting the amino group of propargyl amine was unsuccessful. So *t*-Boc protected propargyl amine was reacted with *cis*-dichloroethylene led the formation of the protected enediyne (**38**) which upon hydrolysis in presence of HCl/NaOH gave title (**40**) compound in 60% yield (Scheme 6). Identity of these compounds were confirmed by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and high-resolution mass spectral data. The cyclization temperatures of the enediynes (**33,35,36**) and (**40**) were measured by DSC and showed remarkable 80 °C variation across the series. The origin of the difference in the thermal reactivity in these enediynes is derived from the steric encumbrance imposed on the alkyne carbon termini by the nitrogen containing substituents at the 1,8 position of the enediyne framework. The enediyne (**33**) undergoes cyclization at 186 °C, substitution of one of the dimethylamino group of (**35**) with 3-hydroxypyridine dramatically reduces the thermal reactivity of the resulting enediyne to 149 °C. The more pronounce trend is observed between the three compounds (**33,36**) and (**40**). Substitution of one dimethylamino group by amino functionality yields a dramatic 47 °C decrease in the thermal reactivity (**36** = 139 °C). Further substitution another dimethylamino group by amino functionality

to form diamino compound (**40**) produces additional 33 °C decrease in the Bergman cyclization temperature (**40** = 106 °C). The enhanced thermal reactivity of diamino enediyne (**40**) results from a combination of the reduced steric hindrance of the primary amine functionality, as well as an additional contribution from the intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

Mg²⁺ modulated thermal cyclization at room temperature

Enediyne ligand **42** (Scheme 7) undergo Bergman cyclization at 106 °C, but thermal reactivity of (**42**) was very striking in presence of metals⁵⁹. Addition of Zn acetate or copper acetate/nitrate to the stirred solution of pyridine enediyne leads to immediate change in the color of the reaction mixture from light brown to black. ¹H NMR of the reaction mixture immediately after addition of Zn salt showed only resonances for the polymerized or decomposed product as broad resonance was observed in the aromatic region. In order to monitor the progress of the reaction, we decided to choose biologically important metal like Mg. In a stirred solution of py-imine enediyne ligand (**42**), solution of MgCl₂ was added slowly and reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 8 h. Solvent was removed at same temperature and solid thus obtained was washed with ether (Scheme 8). MS and NMR (¹H, ¹³C) showed the formation of the Mg²⁺ salt for the enediyne. Solvent from the reaction mixture should be removed at same temperature (0 °C) otherwise decomposition takes place. Either warming up (**44**) to room temperature or addition of Mg²⁺ salt to (**42**) using 20 equivalent of cyclohexadiene as a hydrogen donor in MeOH, led to the formation of new resonance's at 4.99 ppm, and in the aromatic region at 7.35 (m), 7.49–7.54 (m), 8.09 (d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.50 (d) and 8.64 (d) ppm. New resonance at 4.99 ppm is typical for the methylene group attached with imine nitrogen and benzene ring (=N-CH₂Ph)⁶⁰. As soon as reaction proceeds color of the reaction mixture was changed from light brown to dark brown and finally turn to black at the end at this point one broad peak was observed in the aromatic region. Due to high instability of the imine frame work in the reaction condition, it was not possible to check the ¹³C NMR or isolate product at this stage. Nearly 40% maximum conversion was observed after 2 h. In order to increase the stability of the cyclized product in the reaction mixture, we reduced reaction mixture using NaBH₄. Excess of sodium borohydride was added to the reaction mixture at 0–5 °C until reaction mixture becomes light pink in color, if NaBH₄ was added more after achieving the pink color decompo-

sition was observed. In the reaction mixture before reduction with NaBH₄, there was two singlet at 4.88 and 4.99 ppm, but after reduction, resonances at 4.88 and 4.99 ppm were disappeared, and four new singlet at 4.02, 3.97, 3.89, and 3.68 ppm were observed. Out of these four singlet two singlet at 4.02 and 3.68 ppm were assigned for the reduced enediyne (**43**), while two singlet at 3.97 and 3.89 ppm were assigned for the Bergman cyclization product (**46**). These two resonance's at 3.97 and 3.89 ppm perfectly matches with the literature compound,

which further confirmed that there is a cyclized product in the reaction mixture.

Cyclic enediynes and their antibacterial activity

Most of the work on enediyne chemistry is centered around the thermal reactivity modulation and anticancer activity evaluations, but very little is known about the biological importance of thermally stable enediynes. In order to study biological significance of thermally stable enediynes, we have synthesized 12- and 13-membered

cyclic enediynes, and studied their antibacterial activity⁶¹. Scheme 9 illustrates the strategy for the preparation of the 13-membered cyclic enediynes. Reaction of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (**48**) with 1,8-dibromo-oct-4-ene-1,6-diyne⁵¹ in presence of K_2CO_3 afforded desired 13-membered cyclic enediyne (**50**) in 62% yield, which on reduction with $NaBH_4$ in MeOH affords corresponding alcohol (**53**). However, under identical reaction conditions, reaction of resorcinol (**47**) with 1,8-dibromo-oct-4-ene-1,6-diyne⁵¹ results in the decomposition of dibromoenediyne precursor. Alternatively, the desired 13-membered cyclic enediyne (**49**) was synthesized by different approach, using propargyl bromide and resorcinol as starting material (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Reaction of resorcinol (**47**) with propargyl bromide in dry DMF in the presence of K_2CO_3 lead to the formation of **51** in 92% yield. Sonogashira coupling of 2.2 equivalents of **51** with *cis*-1,2-dichloroethylene over a $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ catalyst in the presence of CuI and $BuNH_2$ generates **49** in 66% yield. The identity of these compounds was confirmed spectroscopically. Compounds **49**, **50** and **53** were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains and these compounds exhibits potent antibacterial activity (Table 1). In order to study the effect of different substituents in the aromatic ring on antibacterial activity, we planned to derivatise compound **50**. Surprisingly, reaction of cyclic enediyne **50** with primary amines did not work even at elevated temperatures. Then desired enediynes (**58-65**) were prepared by different approach as shown in Scheme 10. Imines (**54-57**) used for the synthesis of cyclic enediynes were prepared by literature method.

Reaction of substituted imines (**54-57**) with 1,8-dibromo-oct-4-ene-1,6-diyne⁵¹ in presence of K_2CO_3 in

dry DMF lead to the formation of desired products in moderate yields as shown in Scheme 10. After usual work up the crude product was washed with water and purified over SiO_2 column. The cyclic imine enediynes (**58-61**) were reduced to amine derivatives (**62-65**) using $NaBH_4$ in methanol.

Scheme 10

Compound **49**, **50** and **53** exhibited good activity against *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium* but only compound **49** and **50** (in which R group is -CHO and -CH₂OH respectively) exhibit potent activity against *S. aureus*. Terminal hydroxyl group present in **50** may be playing a role in killing mechanism, in comparison to compound **49**. In the series of cyclic imine enediynes compounds (**58-61**) displayed weak activity against *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium* but activity in case of compound **61** (where R = H) increases two fold higher than compound **58**. All of the cyclic amine enediynes displayed higher MIC values as compared to their cyclic imine counterparts. For example compound **62** possess much lower MIC value than compound **58**. In similar manner compound **65** has much higher antimicrobial activity than compound **58**. Moreover only compound **62** and **65** has potent activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This suggests unsaturation around nitrogen is not required for antimicrobial activity of these synthetic compounds. The antimicrobial activity data indicates that compounds **49**, **53**, **62** and **65** were most effective and other displayed moderate activity while **60**, **63** and **64** exhibited scarce activity. Compound **65** was found to be the most active among this series. In order to understand the origin of antibacterial activity of these cyclic enediynes, antibacterial activity of control compounds **51**, and **52** were determined. Compound **52** has been used as an intermediate in the synthesis of cyclic enediyne (**50**), and simple resorcinol ethers (**51,52**)

were found inactive upto 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. So, we believe that the antibacterial activity of these cyclic enediynes is due to the presence of enediyne moiety (Fig. 2), not due to the resorcinol ether (Table 1)⁶¹.

Microwave assisted enediyne synthesis

Microwave assisted synthesis has gained much attention in recent years, as it reduces reaction time from hours to minutes. Sonogashira coupling have been used extensively in the synthesis of enediynes, which requires longer reaction time, and benzene as a solvent in most of the times. In order to make the synthetic procedure more

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of cyclic enediynes

Sl. no.	MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (ATCC, 11775)	<i>E. coli</i> (ATCC, 25668)	<i>S. aureus</i> (clinical isolate)	<i>S. typhimurium</i> (clinical isolate)
51	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
52	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
49	*	4	*	8
50	*	256	8	128
53	*	8	4	128
58	*	256	*	128
59	nd	nd	nd	nd
60	*	*	*	128
61	128	128	128	64
62	32	4	16	128
63	*	64	*	512
64	*	128	*	*
65	16	4	8	16
21*	1	2	2	0.5

21* Tetracycline was used as a reference compound.

nd MIC not determined.

*MIC no activity up to 512 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Fig. 2

eco-friendly, we explored the possibility of enediyne synthesis under microwave irradiation conditions⁶². The starting alkynes (**66-73**) used in the synthesis of acyclic enediynes, were prepared by literature or modified literature methods. Commercially available alcohols/phenols/thiophenol were treated with propargyl bromide in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 in dry DMF or NaH in dry THF. The reaction was stirred at room temperature and progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After usual work up of the reaction mixture, the crude product was purified over silica gel column (Scheme 11). These alkynes (**66-73**) were used in the preparation of symmetrical or asymmetrical enediynes.

Scheme 11

Scheme 12 illustrates the synthesis of chloro-en-yne precursor (**74,75**) and symmetrical enediynes (**76,77**). A typical procedure for the synthesis of chloro-en-yne precursors (**74,75**), involves microwave irradiation (650 W) of a screw capped reaction vessel containing mixture of *cis*-dichloroethylene, substituted alkynes (1 equivalent each), catalytic amount of $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, CuI and *n*- BuNH_2 in benzene. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. Reaction completes in 3–5 min and crude product was purified by silica gel chromatography. The isolated yields of the chloro-en-yne precursor (**74,75**) were ranged from 60–62% along with the symmetrical enediynes (**76, 77, 11, 12**) in 9–13% yield.

Scheme 12

Compounds **74** and **75** were earlier prepared in 70% and 40% yield respectively using copper acetylides and chloro-iodo-ethylene as starting materials⁵¹. When 0.5 equivalent of *cis*-dichloroethylene was reacted with 1.0 equivalent of substituted alkynes under identical reaction conditions as discussed above, 61–65% of the symmetrical enediynes (**76,77**) were obtained along with 6–8% of the chloro-en-yne precursor (**74,75**). Enediyne **77** was earlier prepared in 59% yield using conventional methodology and reaction completed in 16 h⁶³. Asymmetrical enediynes were synthesized in good yields as the procedure described above and shown in Scheme 13.

Scheme 13

All of these reactions were also performed in PEG 400, and comparable yield of the product was obtained.

Considerable progress is expected in this direction in

future, especially biological evaluation of thermally stable enediynes need to be explored more thoroughly. Work is in progress to synthesize enediyne triazole conjugates, and to assess the biological activity of these enediynes.

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Table 2. Symmetrical and asymmetrical enediynes

Compd.	R	R'	Yield (%)	Ref.
77			62	51
78			65	-
79			54	-
80			52	-
81			64	-
82		SiMe ₃	66	-
83			56	-
84			63	63
85			52	-
86			62	-
87			59	-
88		SiMe ₃	65	-

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